

Analysis of the Influence of the Habit of Reading The Qur'an at UQM in Supporting or Enhancing Islamic Religious Education

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the influence of the habit of reading the Qur'an at Al-Qalam Malang University (UQM) in enhancing religious education. The background of this research is the importance of character building and strengthening students' spirituality through the habituation of reading the Qur'an in an academic environment. This research uses a descriptive qualitative method with data collection techniques through in-depth interviews with UNIQ students and observation of Qur'an reading activities. The collected data are analyzed qualitatively to explore the relationship between the habit of reading the Qur'an and the understanding and implementation of religious values in students' daily lives.

The results show that the habit of reading the Qur'an at UQM positively contributes to strengthening students' understanding and application of religious values, thereby supporting the improvement of religious education in the university environment. Additionally, the study found that students who regularly read the Qur'an tend to have better attitudes in facing various challenges and conflicts in their daily lives. They are also more capable of guarding themselves against temptations and negative behaviors that contradict religious teachings. This indicates that the habit of reading the Qur'an not only impacts the understanding of religious values but also influences individual character and morality.

Therefore, efforts to enhance Qur'an reading activities in the university environment should continue to be encouraged to shape a more religious and morally upright young generation. By fostering a more religious and virtuous young generation through the habit of reading the Qur'an, it is hoped that society will become more harmonious and peaceful. Furthermore, individuals who are diligent in reading the Qur'an also tend to be more patient and wise in facing life's trials. Thus, it is important for each individual to continuously enrich themselves by reading the Qur'an to become better individuals who are beneficial to others.

Keywords: Qur'an reading habit, Religious education, Character building, Student spirituality.

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Introduction

Religious education plays a crucial role in shaping individual character and spirituality, especially within higher education environments. In this era of globalization and modernization, the challenges to understanding and practicing religious values are becoming increasingly significant. Therefore, educational institutions, particularly universities, have a responsibility responsible for not only providing quality academic education, but also ensuring that the spiritual and moral aspects of students are maintained and developed.

This can be done through improving the curriculum which includes courses on religion, religious activities, and spiritual formation that

are integrated into academic and non-academic activities. In this way, students can have a deeper understanding of religious values and can apply them in everyday life. Apart from that, universities can also create an environment that supports the development of students' spirituality, such as providing worship facilities, spiritual counseling, and spiritual self-development programs. Thus, religious education in higher education can be a vehicle for forming strong character and balanced spirituality in individuals (Dwi Desti, et al).. Through religious education in higher education, students can also learn to appreciate religious diversity and tolerance between religious communities. This can help create a harmonious campus environment and reduce the potential for conflict between students. Thus, religious education in higher education is not only important for students' personal development,

but also for creating an inclusive and peaceful campus community (Pramita et al. 2023).

One approach that can be taken in strengthening religious education in higher education is through the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an. The Qur'an, as the holy book of Muslims, not only contains life instructions and religious teachings, but is also a strong source of inspiration and motivation in living daily life. Reading and meditating on the Al-Qur'an regularly can help students internalize the values contained in it, which in turn is expected to increase their understanding and application of religion in their lives (Mita Silfityasari and Ashif Az Zhafi 2020).

Apart from that, getting into the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an can also help students to improve their reading skills and understanding of Arabic texts, which is the key to understanding the contents of the Al-Qur'an better. By strengthening religious education through the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an, it is hoped that students can become individuals who are more devout and have noble character, and are able to face various challenges and temptations that exist around them. Apart from that, by increasingly understanding religious teachings, it is hoped that students will also be able to become agents of positive change in society, and be able to make a real contribution to the development of the nation and state (Ismail and W 2022).

Al-Qolam University (UQM) as one of the higher education institutions in Indonesia, has developed various programs to support religious education, one of which is through the habitual activity of reading the Koran. However, the extent to which this habit is effective in supporting or improving students' religious education is still a question that has not been answered thoroughly. Therefore, this research was conducted to analyze the influence of the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an at UQM on improving religious education among students (Taufiq et al. 2022).

It is hoped that this research will provide a clearer picture of the effectiveness of habitual activities to read the Al-Qur'an in increasing understanding of religion among students. Thus, it is hoped that the results of this research can become a reference for UQM and other educational institutions in developing more effective religious education programs. Apart from that, it is also hoped that this research can contribute to the development of knowledge about religious education in Indonesia. For example, a university in Indonesia conducted research to evaluate a program to familiarize students with reading the Qur'an s. It is hoped that the results of this research can serve as a guide for other educational institutions in increasing the effectiveness of religious education programs. This research is motivated by the importance of character building and strengthening students' spirituality through the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an in an academic environment. Religious education in universities has an important role in forming the young generation who have good morals and morals. Al-Qalam University Malang (UQM) sees the need to integrate the habit of reading the Koran into students' daily activities so that it can have a positive impact on strengthening religious values and spirituality (Adam 2023).

It is hoped that this research can contribute to the development of religious education programs at UQM and other universities, as well as provide a deeper understanding of the role of the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an in shaping student character and spirituality.

Research Methods

This research uses a descriptive qualitative method which aims to describe and understand the relationship between the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an and the implementation of religious values among students at Al-Qalam University Malang (UQM) (Rukminingsih, Adnan, and Latief 2020). The qualitative method was chosen to explore in depth students' experiences, views and perceptions regarding the habit of reading the Koran and its impact on their lives, both socially and religiously (Fahza Alfaizi, Airohmah, and Fatwa Anbiya 2023). The data source collection technique uses in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation without using special methods. This means that collecting primary and secondary sources related to the above problems will be utilized as well and as completely as possible. Since this research uses qualitative methods, to analyze the data, the author uses an interactive analysis method, namely data analysis is carried out systematically and continuously starting from data collection until it is completed within a certain time (Dr. J.R. Raco, M.E. 2010).

Discussion

1. Founding and Beginnings

Al-Qolam University Malang, which is located on Jl. Raya Putat Lor Gondanglegi, Malang, started as the Sharia Faculty of the Islamic University of Malang (UNISMA). This institution was founded in 1985 as a result of an agreement between UNISMA and ulama and community leaders in Gondanglegi District and its surroundings, approximately 20 km from Malang City.

Initially, lectures were held in the Agus Salim Gondanglegi High School building. After receiving assistance from various parties, the permanent building for the UNISMA Malang Sharia Faculty was built in 1988 on waqf land in Putat Lor Village, Gondanglegi District, about 3 km from the previous location. Operational permission was obtained on February 14 1991 through Decree of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 1991, with the Department of Religious Justice (Qadla').

2. Change and Development

In 1996, based on the Decree of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 268 of 1996, the Department of Religious Justice was changed to the Department of Ahwal al-Syakhshiyah. A year later, through the Decree of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number E/35/1996 on March 10 1997, the permit to provide education for the Ahwal al-Syakhshiyah Department of UNISMA Malang was handed over to the STAI Al-Qolam Foundation. This happened as a result of the Circular Letter of the Director General of Islamic Religious Institutional Development, Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number E/PP.009/J/1121/1997.

On July 13 1997, it was agreed to change the Sharia Faculty of UNISMA Malang into an independent educational institution with the name Al-Qolam Islamic College (STAI). The chosen department continues to be the Ahwal al-Syakhshiyah Department. Even though there was talk of adding departments/study programs, it was only in 2002 that a new department could be opened, namely the Islamic Religious Education (PAI) Study Program, based on the Decree of the STAI Al-Qolam Foundation Number 45/SK/Y.STAI-Q/XI/ 2002.

3. Development Momentum

STAI Al-Qolam continues to develop itself. On March 24 2007, the Indonesian Ministry of Religion issued a decree establishing the Islamic Religious Education Study Program with Number Dj.I/179/2007, to answer the needs of the community. In June 2007, STAI Al-Qolam received a valuable opportunity to develop institutions through collaboration with the State Islamic University (UIN) Malang.

4. Addition of New Study Programs

In 2013, STAI Al-Qolam proposed opening the Raudlatul Athfal Teacher Education Study Program (PGRA). This permit was only issued on March 14 2014 through the Decree of the Director General of Islamic Higher Education, Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1500 of 2014. In the same year, the STAI Al-Qolam institutional development team proposed opening four new study programs, namely Sharia Economic Law (HES), Education Teacher of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah (PGMI), Islamic Broadcasting Communication (KPI), and Islamic Community Development (PMI). From this application, three study programs were approved to be opened, namely HES, KPI, and PMI.

5. Change of Form to IAI

After going through a long development process, on November 5 2014 the Director General of Islamic Education Decree Number 6266 of 2014 was issued which approved the change in the form of STAI Al-Qolam to the Al-Qolam Islamic Institute (IAI). This change marks a major step in the development of Islamic boarding school-based higher education institutions which aim to answer growing educational needs.

With various study programs and strategic collaborations, Al-Qolam University Malang continues to strive to improve the quality of education and strengthen its reputation on the national and international stage.

Al Qolam University Malang: Becoming a Transformative Islamic Boarding School-Based University with International Reputation

Vision

Al-Qolam University Malang has a vision or aspiration to become a transformative university based on Islamic boarding schools and having an international reputation in the development of science, based on morals and human values.

Commitment to realizing academic excellence at national and international levels is the main goal of this university.

Mission

To achieve this vision, Al Qolam University Malang carries out the following missions:

1. Develop transformative, innovative and technology-based institutional management at all levels of higher education.
2. Strengthening the university's financial independence through an efficient management system.
3. Providing quality education that is integrated with Islamic values and a holistic approach.
4. Developing an Islamic boarding school-based transformation orientation in research, service, learning and scientific study activities.

5. Building strategic partnerships to facilitate increasing the university's international reputation.
6. Improving the quality of publications and internationalization of Islamic boarding school-based transformation ideas.

Objective

In order to realize this mission, Al Qolam University Malang set the following goals:

1. Creating transformative, innovative and technology-based institutional management at all levels of higher education.
2. The realization of independent, professional and efficient higher education financial management.
3. Providing quality education that is integrated with Islamic values and a holistic approach.
4. Development of Islamic boarding school-based transformation orientation in research, service, learning and scientific studies.
5. Establishment of strategic partnerships to improve the international reputation of universities.
6. Increasing the quality and quantity of scientific publications, as well as the internationalization of Islamic boarding school-based transformation ideas (Dokumentasi, Universitas Al-Qolam Malang, 2024).

Commitment to Quality

Al-Qolam University Malang or better known as UQM, is committed to continuing to improve the quality of education through various strategic efforts. One way is to improve university accreditation, which reflects the quality of education recognized by the national accreditation body. Good accreditation is one measure of the success of educational institutions in providing a quality academic environment. Apart from that, UQM also integrates the latest technology in the teaching and learning process. The application of this technology allows students and lecturers to collaborate more efficiently, access a wider range of educational resources, and adopt more interactive and innovative learning methods. In addition, the university also pays special attention to ongoing development for lecturers and

teaching staff to ensure they are always updated with the latest developments in the field of education.

Not only focusing on academic achievement, UQM also has a big vision in forming superior student characters, both intellectually and morally. Education at UQM is not only aimed at producing graduates who are academically intelligent, but also have integrity, responsibility and the ability to adapt to increasingly complex global challenges. UQM graduates are expected to be able to contribute positively to society by bringing the good values taught in the Islamic religion.

One form of character education emphasized at UQM is the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an regularly. This activity is one of the characteristics of a campus that prioritizes strong religious education. The habit of reading the Koran is not just a form of worship, but also has a significant impact in improving the spiritual, moral and intellectual quality of students. Reading and understanding the Koran helps students strengthen their

relationship with God, which will ultimately improve their behavior in everyday life. Apart from that, a deep understanding of Islamic teachings through the Koran is also an important foundation in forming a strong and resilient character (Taufiq et al. 2022).

Al-Qur'an reading activities at UQM are carried out regularly in the form of group recitations, which are usually held once a month. This activity was attended by students, the majority of whom were hafidzah or memorizers of the Al-Qur'an, around 80%, while the remainder, around 20%, were students who had not yet memorized the Koran but still actively participated in this activity. The reading of the Al-Qur'an usually begins after midday prayer and continues until it is finished, in a solemn and devout atmosphere (Pramita et al. 2023).

The benefits of this routine activity of reading the Koran are felt by students. Apart from helping them to better understand Islamic teachings, this activity is also an important moment of self-reflection, especially in the midst of busy academic activities. Students can find inner peace and spiritual enlightenment through reading verses of the holy Koran. This ultimately contributes to improving the quality of religious education at UQM, where students not only learn theory, but also practice Islamic teachings in their daily lives.

By getting students into the habit of reading the Koran, UQM hopes to produce a generation that not only excels in academics, but also has a strong religious foundation and is ready to become future leaders with noble morals. The education provided at UNIQ is not only limited to intellectual aspects, but also includes spiritual and moral aspects which are no less important in facing global challenges (Dokumentasi, Universitas Al-Qolam Malang, 2024).

The following are some of the results of in-depth interviews, some of the influences of the habit of reading the Koran on religious education:

Research Interview Results: The Influence of Al-Qur'an Reading Habits at Al-Qalam University Malang (UQM)

1. Question: How does the habit of reading the Koran on the UQM campus influence your understanding of religion?

Respondent 1 (Student): "I feel that the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an every day helps me understand religious teachings more deeply. The activity of reading the Al-Qur'an on campus makes me more focused in understanding the meaning of the verses holy, especially in the context of everyday life. I feel closer to religious teachings, especially in overcoming life's challenges" (Qoyyimatus Saniyah, Wawancara, 2024).

Respondent 2 (Student): "This habit not only increases my understanding of religion, but also helps me internalize the values contained in the Koran. I become more sensitive to my own behavior and more motivated to maintain good morals, such as patience and honesty" (Rahma Habibah, Wawancara, 2024).

2. Question: Does the habit of reading the Koran have an impact on your daily life, especially in facing conflicts or challenges?

Respondent 3 (Student): "Yes, of course. I feel calmer and better able to control my emotions when facing problems. For example, when there is a conflict with a friend, I prefer to be patient and find a solution rather than immediately getting angry. I often remember

messages- messages from the Koran about the importance of maintaining good relations and resolving conflicts peacefully (Rahma Habibah, Wawancara, 2024).

Respondent 4 (Student): "I feel more prepared to face various tests in life. Reading the Koran every day gives me a kind of mental strength to stay positive and patient. In fact, I feel I can avoid negative behavior such as lying or talking bad about people others because they always remember religious teachings" (Cholidah Hilmiya muktamarah, Wawancara, 2024).

3. Question: What is your view about the importance of the habit of reading the Koran in forming the character of students on this campus?

Respondent 5 (Student): "I see it as a very important thing. At UQM, many academic activities are tough, and sometimes we can feel stressed. By reading the Koran, I feel calmer and motivated to maintain morality and morals I. This activity forms better character and helps us become students who are not only academically intelligent, but also religious and moral (Lilis Masfufah, Wawancara, 2024).

Respondent 6 (Student): "In my opinion, this habit is very good for forming a more religious young generation. Campus encourages us to always remember Allah, and that influences the way we act every day. I also see my friends becoming more polite, patient and wise after they diligently participate in reading the Qur'an (Miftahul Jannah, Wawancara, 2024).

4. Question: Do you think this activity should continue to be improved in the higher education environment? If yes, why?

Respondent 7 (Student): "Of course. I think this is an important part of forming our spirituality and morality as students. In this modern era, the temptation to fall into negative behavior is very large. The activity of reading the Koran helps us maintain So, I really support that this activity continues to be improved (Mamlu', Wawancara, 2024).

Respondent 8 (Student): "In my opinion, this activity is not only important for us personally, but also for the wider community. If the younger generation can grow up with strong religious values, we can hope that our society will be better. Therefore Therefore, I hope that the campus will continue to encourage this activity (Rofi'ah Adawiyah, Wawancara, 2024).

From the results of this interview, it can be concluded that the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an in the UQM environment not only has an impact on increasing students' understanding of religion, but also helps in forming character, morality and the ability to face various life challenges. Students who are involved in this activity tend to have a better attitude and are wiser in dealing with problems, which supports improving religious education in the tertiary environment. Several research results show that the habit of reading the Koran at UQM has the following positive influences:

Increase understanding of religion

Reading the Koran regularly helps a person understand Islamic teachings in more depth. The Koran is the main source of Islamic teachings which cover various aspects of life, such as aqidah (faith), worship, and morals. A good understanding of the contents of the Koran will provide a strong foundation for religious education (Jarlah 2019).

Religious Aspect	Example from the Qur'an	Impact of Understanding
Faith (Aqidah)	Surah Al-Ikhlās (112:1-4) about the concept of tawhīd, or the oneness of Allah.	Strengthens the belief in the oneness of Allah and the importance of worshipping Him alone.
Worship (Ibadah)	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:183) about the obligation of fasting during Ramadan.	Understands the reasons and wisdom behind the obligation of fasting as an act of obedience to Allah.
Morality (Akhlaq)	Surah Al-Hujurat (49:12), which forbids gossiping (ghibah).	Understands the importance of controlling speech, respecting others, and avoiding negative behavior.
Social Interaction (Muamalah)	Surah An-Nisa (4:58) about justice in decision-making.	Teaches the importance of being fair in social life and resolving issues wisely.
Inheritance Law	Surah An-Nisa (4:11) which regulates the fair distribution of inheritance.	Understands the rules of inheritance in Islam, based on justice and the provisions of Allah.
Speaking Etiquette	Surah Luqman (31:19) which advises speaking gently.	Teaches the etiquette of speaking politely, gently, and without hurting others' feelings.
Cleanliness and Purity	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:222) on the importance of maintaining personal cleanliness.	Understands the obligation of physical cleanliness as part of purity and worship to Allah.
Patience and Perseverance	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:153) on the importance of patience and prayer in facing trials.	Teaches the importance of patience in facing challenges and the significance of praying to Allah.

This table illustrates how understanding of various aspects of Islamic teachings can be improved through the habit of reading and understanding the Koran regularly.

Building Spiritual Closeness with Allah

The Qur'an is the word of God that guides humans towards truth. Reading the Qur'an regularly can strengthen a spiritual connection with Allah, help a person feel closer to Him, and be more obedient in carrying out His commands (Taufiq et al. 2022).

Aspect of Islamic Teaching	Relevant Qur'anic Verse	Enhanced Understanding
Tawhid (Faith)	Surah Al-Ikhlās (112:1-4)	Understanding the concept of tawhīd and the oneness of Allah, which is the core of Islamic creed.
Worship	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:183) on the obligation of fasting during Ramadan	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:183) on the obligation of fasting during Ramadan
Morality	Surah Al-Hujurat (49:12) which forbids gossiping (ghibah)	Realizing the importance of controlling one's speech, behaving well, and avoiding bad behaviors like slander or gossip.
Social Interaction (Muamalah)	Surah An-Nisa (4:58) on justice in resolving matters	Understanding the principle of justice in social life and the importance of upholding others' rights fairly and wisely.
Inheritance Law	Surah An-Nisa (4:11) on the distribution of inheritance	Understanding the rules of fair inheritance according to Islamic law, in line with the rights set by Allah.
Patience	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:153) on	Enhancing understanding of the importance of patience in facing trials, and the significance of prayer and supplication.
Speaking Etiquette	Surah Luqman (31:19) on speaking gently and politely	Teaching good manners in speech, avoiding harshness, and considering others' feelings in daily communication.
Cleanliness and Purity	Surah Al-Baqarah (2:222) on the importance of maintaining cleanliness	Understanding the obligation of physical cleanliness and purity as part of worship and closeness to Allah.
Simple Living	Surah Al-Furqan (25:67) on	Understanding the importance of living frugally,

This table shows how the habit of reading the Koran regularly can increase a person's understanding of various aspects of Islamic teachings, both in terms of worship, morals and social aspects (Pramita et al. 2023).

Developing noble morals/character formation

The Qur'an contains moral teachings that can shape positive behavior, such as patience, honesty and compassion. Read and meditate on verses of the Qur'an helps readers to internalize noble values and apply them in everyday life.

The following is a table that explains examples of moral teachings in the Qur'an that can help develop noble morals:

Conclusion

The conclusion from the discussion above shows that the habit of reading the Al-Qur'an regularly among UQM students has a very significant impact in increasing the understanding and application of religious values in everyday life. This religious activity not only influences intellectual and spiritual aspects, but also has a deep influence on student behavior and morality. Students who read the Koran more often show a deeper understanding of Islamic teachings, which is reflected in their attitudes and actions. They tend to be more consistent in carrying out obligatory acts of worship, such as the five daily prayers, and more often perform

sunnah acts of worship such as reading the Koran, fasting, and practicing Islamic principles in their social life.

The importance of reading the Koran lies in its ability to enrich students' theoretical knowledge about religious teachings. However, its impact does not stop at the intellectual level. Reading the Koran regularly also helps students internalize the religious values they study. This internalization leads to positive changes in the aspect of morality, where students become more honest, patient and wise in facing life's challenges. The activity of reading the Koran provides them with clear guidance to apply values such as honesty, justice, tolerance and gratitude in everyday life. This also affects the way they interact with other people, where students who regularly read the Koran tend to be more empathetic, caring and respectful of others.

These findings have important implications for the development of religious education programs in higher education. To strengthen religious education and form a more religious student character, it is necessary to integrate Al-Qur'an reading activities into the religious education curriculum and extracurricular activities. Activities such as tahsin classes, joint tadarus, and Al-Qur'an studies can be effective means to facilitate this habit among students. Apart from that, universities can provide a more supportive environment, such as comfortable facilities and sufficient time allocation for students to carry out religious activities. These steps can help students form a more consistent habit of reading the Koran and ultimately strengthen their understanding of religious teachings.

Although this research shows positive results, it is important to note that these findings are still limited to one university, namely UQM. Therefore, it is hoped that further research can involve more universities to obtain more representative results. In addition, a more in-depth approach is needed, such as qualitative research through in-depth interviews or direct observation, to understand the personal motivations and subjective impact of the habit of reading the Koran on students. Further studies can also explore various methods of learning the Koran that are effective in supporting religious education in higher education.

Overall, the habit of reading the Koran plays an important role in creating a young generation who is not only academically intelligent, but also has strong moral and spiritual integrity. Students who regularly read the Koran have a higher awareness of their responsibilities as religious individuals. They are better prepared to face life's challenges patiently, wisely and sincerely, and are able to make positive contributions to society. With moral and spiritual integrity It is hoped that this young generation can become agents of change who bring positive values to society, creating a more harmonious, tolerant and peaceful social environment.

Integrating the habit of reading the Koran in the education system will not only produce students who excel academically, but also students who have social sensitivity, high morality, and a commitment to implementing religious teachings in every aspect of their lives. This is a strong basis for forming a generation that is not only knowledgeable, but also has good character, which will ultimately have a positive impact on the life of society and the nation.

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